

THE SONAR TECHNOLOGY AND USE OF NAUTICAL CHARTS

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Introduction

Over the recent past, the popular media have been busy learning about the science of the ocean. The results from analysts show that much has not been discovered about the ocean. It has been said that the research for the nautical charts and the sonar technology has increased tremendously. The popular media is trying to investigate how to make the science of oceanography better than what is known (Dong, 2018).

The main topics that I will discuss in this paper will include the science behind the sonar technology and the use of nautical charts. To begin with, sonar technology may be a new term to many but it simply means the science of using the sound propagation to detect and trace objects under the sea. When diver ventures deep into the sea, there is always the need to communicate from the surface of the water to keep in contact. The science of oceanography uses this technology to ease the communication process.

On the other hand, the science of using the nautical charts has been explored by the popular media in the current world. People are trying to inquire about the science behind these charts. Nautical charts refer to the situation where the stakeholders involved in the ocean exploration use the aspect of hydrogen surveys to generate the nautical charts. Nautical charts are used to show graphic design for the maritime of the coastal region (Smith, 2018).

The body

The use of sonar technology has been seen to be the most explored item by the popular media. As briefly discussed above, sonar technology refers to the use of sound propagation to detect, navigate or communicate with a certain explorer and locating an object in the deep oceanic water. In the recent past, people have been always trying to know about this technology in detail. This is because most people have a growing concern for what is happening in the oceans including how information is sourced from the deep oceanic floors. Many times explorers tend to dive as deep as the oceanic beds to give the feedback of how it looks like, what grows there and many more things and process that happen down there (Pelin, 2018).

How the sonar technology work

Sonar technology mainly makes the use of echo to transmit the sound from one object to another. For example, when sound is produced from one point, it is transferred to the nearby environment. When the sound encounters an object in the environment it is produced, it is reflected back to the object that produced it. This is the same phenomena that we actually experience as we hear our voice echoed back when we speak loudly. Ocean animals like whales and dolphins and specialized machines that are used to explore the oceans use these waves to detect an object nearby them including their shape and size at large.

The main waves used in the sonar technology

The sonar technology uses the sonar and the radar waves. Both sonar and radar are used by the oceanographers to locate objects in the ocean using the sonar technology. Radar is derived from the first three letters of radio detection and ranging. Radar generally uses those radio waves to enhance the sonar technology. The meaning of detection here actually refers to locate objects in the oceans by the use of the radio signals. On the other hand, the sonar waves use the

waves of the echo that is produced from one point to detect the distance of an object in regard to its distance and specific location.

The radar

Radar generally is composed of the transmitter, a specific antenna, a screen, and a receiver. These components work hand in hand to locate the image as expected by the oceanographers. For instance, the radar systems produce a given sound which in turn is reflected by a nearby object. Since radar has antennae, it detects the echo waves that are produced from the reflector to the receiver. The receiver, in turn, encodes the sound and displays the information on the screen as needed by the oceanographers.

The sonar

Sonar is delivered from the first three letters of the sound navigator ranging. As radar systems, the sonar system can locate marine animals and objects deep in the sea and estimate their distance.

Another second most explored thing by the popular media is the use of the nautical charts in the oceanic environment. Nautical charts the science of the hydrogen surveys include the graphic designs about the maritime of the oceanic environment. These charts are mostly used by the boaters to locate different maps in the coastal regions. They are recommended by the coastal navigators as they provide sufficient information about different maps that are available in the coastal region.

Over the recent past, the nautical charts have been seen to undergo a series of modifications as informed by the private and public surveys. Both the private and public sectors are involved in the contribution of the information needed regarding the generation of the required maps.

The nautical charts are used by the sailors on a daily basis. The information that nautical charts generate include the location of obstacles such as the mountains and coastal lines, the sea depths and potential sea routes to follow. This information is quite important as it helps avoid accidents and uncertainties in the oceans (Masetti, 2018).

References

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